

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No5(5)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 716 sahifa,
22-may, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
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“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
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va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
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reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
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Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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USING INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ORGANIZING LABORATORY CLASSES IN ZOOLOGY

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Abstract: This article analyzes the pedagogical opportunities of using innovative educational technologies in organizing laboratory classes in Zoology. The role of modern pedagogical technologies in improving the practical training of pre-service biology teachers, developing their research skills, and fostering professional competencies is highlighted. The study demonstrates that the integration of problem-based learning, project-based learning, the STEAM approach, digital technologies, and virtual laboratories contributes significantly to enhancing the effectiveness of students' practical activities. The findings indicate that innovative educational technologies promote active learning, independent inquiry, critical thinking, and the acquisition of practical skills necessary for future professional practice in biology education.

Key words: zoology, laboratory classes, innovative technologies, competency-based approach, virtual laboratory, STEAM, biology education, research activity.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada zoologiya fanidan laboratoriya mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishda innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan. Bo'lajak biologiya o'qituvchilarining amaliy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish, tadqiqotchilik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish hamda kasbiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarning o'рни yoritilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari muammoli ta'lim, loyihaviy ta'lim, STEAM yondashuvi, raqamli texnologiyalar va virtual laboratoriyalarni integratsiyalash talabalarning amaliy faoliyati samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshirishini ko'rsatdi. Olingan natijalar innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari faol o'qitish, mustaqil izlanish, tanqidiy fikrlash hamda biologiya ta'limidagi kelajakdagi kasbiy faoliyat uchun zarur bo'lgan amaliy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishga xizmat qilishini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: zoologiya, laboratoriya mashg'ulotlari, innovatsion texnologiyalar, kompetensiyaviy yondashuv, virtual laboratoriya, STEAM, biologiya ta'limi, tadqiqotchilik faoliyati.

Аннотация: В данной статье проанализированы педагогические возможности использования инновационных образовательных технологий при организации лабораторных занятий по зоологии. Освещена роль современных педагогических технологий в совершенствовании практической подготовки будущих учителей биологии, развитии их исследовательских навыков и формировании профессиональных компетенций. Результаты исследования показывают, что интеграция проблемного обучения, проектного обучения, подхода STEAM, цифровых технологий и виртуальных лабораторий значительно повышает эффективность практической деятельности студентов. Полученные данные свидетельствуют о том, что инновационные образовательные технологии способствуют активному обучению, самостоятельному исследованию, развитию критического мышления и формированию практических навыков, необходимых для будущей профессиональной деятельности в области биологического образования.

Ключевые слова: зоология, лабораторные занятия, инновационные технологии, компетентностный подход, виртуальная лаборатория, STEAM, биологическое образование, исследовательская деятельность.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, large-scale reforms are being implemented to modernize the higher education system, develop the professional competencies of future teachers, and improve the quality of education in accordance with international standards. These reforms require the enhancement of pedagogical education content, the integration of innovative educational technologies into the teaching process, and the strengthening of students' practical training. In preparing students majoring in biology education to meet the demands of contemporary schools, Zoology occupies a particularly important place.

Zoology is one of the fundamental disciplines within the system of biological sciences, focusing on the study of animal diversity, taxonomy, anatomy, morphology, physiology, ecology, and evolutionary development.

The knowledge acquired through the study of Zoology provides a solid foundation that enables future biology teachers to explain biological processes scientifically and effectively to school students.

However, the teaching of Zoology should not be limited solely to the transmission of theoretical knowledge. It is equally important to develop students' practical skills, including observing, comparing, and analyzing biological objects, using laboratory equipment, preparing biological specimens, and drawing scientific conclusions. Laboratory classes serve as the primary means of connecting theoretical knowledge with practical activities, enhancing students' research potential, and developing their professional competencies.

In recent years, the introduction of digital technologies, virtual laboratories, electronic learning platforms, artificial intelligence tools, and STEAM technologies into the educational process has significantly expanded the possibilities for organizing laboratory classes. These technologies help transform students into active participants in the learning process, promote independent inquiry, and foster the development of research skills.

Moreover, innovative educational technologies create opportunities for visualizing complex biological processes, simulating laboratory experiments, and providing students with access to diverse learning resources. Such opportunities are particularly important in Zoology, where direct observation, experimentation, and practical investigation are essential components of effective learning. Therefore, the use of innovative educational technologies in organizing Zoology laboratory classes has become one of the most relevant issues in modern biology education and teacher training.

However, practical experience shows that in some cases, Zoology laboratory classes are still organized in a traditional manner, where students are mainly limited to acquiring ready-made information. This situation hinders the full development of their competencies in independent thinking, problem-solving, conducting scientific observations, and analyzing biological processes.

This circumstance highlights the need to develop and implement scientific and methodological foundations for organizing Zoology laboratory classes based on innovative pedagogical technologies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical and methodological foundations of innovative educational technologies have been studied by many scholars. In particular, John Raven emphasized the importance of competency-based education in developing learners' ability to apply knowledge in real-life situations. Franz E. Weinert highlighted competencies as an integration of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values necessary for effective professional performance.

In the field of biology education, scholars such as N. A. Muslimov, B. X. Xodjayev, and O. Q. Tolipov have investigated the pedagogical conditions for developing professional competencies through innovative teaching technologies. Their studies indicate that project-based learning, problem-based learning, and digital technologies significantly improve students' practical and research skills.

Recent studies also emphasize the effectiveness of the STEAM approach and virtual laboratories in organizing biology and Zoology education. However, the methodological aspects of integrating innovative educational technologies into Zoology laboratory classes require further research and practical implementation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted on the basis of competency-based, systemic, activity-oriented, and innovative approaches. The methodological foundation of the research was formed by the theory of biology education, the concept of competency-based education, constructivist learning theory, and modern pedagogical technologies.

During the research process, the current state of organizing Zoology laboratory classes was analyzed, and pedagogical factors contributing to the development of students' practical preparedness were identified.

The following research methods were employed:

- analysis of pedagogical, biological, and methodological literature;
- examination of normative-legal documents and educational curricula;
- observation;
- interviews;
- questionnaire surveys;
- expert evaluation;
- pedagogical experimentation;
- mathematical and statistical analysis.

In addition, innovative technologies used in organizing Zoology laboratory classes were classified, and their pedagogical effectiveness was evaluated.

Within the framework of the study, the following criteria were developed to assess students' laboratory competencies:

1. **Motivational Criterion** - students' interest in laboratory activities, inclination toward biological research, and level of professional motivation;
2. **Cognitive Criterion** - the level of mastery of zoological knowledge and understanding of scientific concepts;
3. **Activity-Based Criterion** - the quality of working with laboratory equipment, preparing biological specimens, and performing practical tasks;
4. **Reflective Criterion** - the ability to analyze completed work, identify mistakes, and draw independent conclusions.

These criteria made it possible to comprehensively evaluate students' readiness for practical activities and determine the effectiveness of innovative educational technologies in the development of professional competencies among future biology teachers.

During the experimental phase of the study, a variety of innovative educational approaches were integrated into laboratory classes, including project-based learning, problem-based learning, the STEAM approach, case-study methods, digital microscopes, virtual laboratories, and interactive presentations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Laboratory classes in Zoology constitute an integral component of biology education and play a significant role in preparing students for scientific observation and experimental activities. The primary purpose of laboratory work is to enable students to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, investigate biological objects, and develop research competencies essential for their future professional careers.

The results of the study demonstrated that the use of innovative technologies significantly increases the effectiveness of laboratory classes.

The implementation of the project-based learning method promotes students' independent learning activities. Students engage in scientific inquiry by studying specific zoological objects, investigating their ecological characteristics, and presenting the obtained results. Such activities foster independent decision-making skills and contribute to the development of scientific thinking.

Laboratory classes organized on the basis of problem-based learning encourage students to discover new knowledge independently rather than merely receiving ready-made information. For example, tasks aimed at identifying the adaptation mechanisms of particular organisms to their habitats stimulate analytical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

The STEAM approach provides opportunities for integrating Zoology with other disciplines. Analyzing biometric characteristics of zoological specimens using statistical methods, processing ecological data through digital platforms, and presenting results in graphical formats contribute to the development of students' scientific research competencies and interdisciplinary thinking.

Virtual laboratories enable students to observe and analyze biological objects remotely. One of their major advantages is the possibility of repeatedly simulating complex biological processes, ensuring compliance with safety requirements, and making more efficient use of laboratory resources. These tools create flexible learning environments that support both individual and collaborative learning activities.

Furthermore, virtual laboratory technologies allow students to conduct experiments that may be difficult, expensive, or impossible to perform under traditional laboratory conditions, thereby expanding educational opportunities and enhancing the quality of practical training in Zoology.

Digital microscopes, mobile applications, QR codes, electronic atlases, and artificial intelligence-based identification software enhance the quality of studying zoological objects. These tools enable students to determine the taxonomic position of animals, analyze their morphological characteristics, and store research results in electronic databases.

The conducted analysis demonstrated that laboratory classes organized on the basis of innovative technologies significantly increase students' engagement, interest, and practical preparedness. Such activities not only strengthen zoological knowledge but also contribute to the development of the professional competencies of future biology teachers.

The effectiveness of organizing Zoology laboratory classes through innovative educational technologies was investigated during the study. The results revealed that, compared with traditional laboratory instruction, the implementation of innovative technologies led to significant improvements in students' learning engagement, independent learning skills, and research competencies.

The application of project-based learning and problem-based learning strategies in laboratory classes enhanced students' ability to analyze biological phenomena and draw scientific conclusions. The quality of practical assignments completed by students and their level of independence increased considerably.

The use of virtual laboratories and digital microscopes contributed to the development of students' skills in identifying zoological specimens, analyzing morphological structures, and explaining biological processes. In particular, the use of digital tools in the study of complex biological objects improved the level of learning and comprehension of educational materials.

During the experimental implementation, the following positive outcomes were observed:

- increased student participation and engagement in laboratory activities;
- improved skills in observing and describing biological objects;
- enhanced proficiency in using microscopes and other laboratory equipment;
- strengthened interest in research and project-based activities;
- development of independent learning skills;
- improved ability to analyze biological processes and draw scientific conclusions;
- increased levels of professional competency development.

These findings indicate that innovative educational technologies create favorable conditions for improving the quality of laboratory instruction, promoting active learning, and preparing future biology teachers for effective professional practice in modern educational environments.

The results of the study indicate that laboratory classes organized through innovative technologies contribute significantly to the development of students' ability to apply knowledge in practical situations and enhance their level of professional preparedness.

Furthermore, the use of innovative technologies enriches the content of laboratory classes and creates opportunities for making the learning process more engaging, interactive, and effective. As a result, students acquire a deeper understanding of zoological concepts and learn to approach biological objects from a scientific perspective.

The findings are consistent with previous research on the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in biology education. According to contemporary educational theories, student-centered and activity-based teaching methods improve learning outcomes and positively influence the formation of professional competencies.

The study demonstrated that project-based learning and problem-based learning possess high pedagogical effectiveness in organizing laboratory classes in Zoology. These approaches not only facilitate knowledge acquisition but also develop students' ability to apply their knowledge in practical and professional contexts.

The discussion further revealed that virtual laboratories and digital technologies can help address several challenges commonly encountered in biology education. For example, the lack of certain zoological specimens, limited laboratory resources, or difficulties associated with observing biological processes under real conditions can be effectively overcome through virtual learning environments.

In addition, laboratory classes organized using the STEAM approach promote interdisciplinary integration and broaden students' scientific perspectives. Consequently, students develop a systematic understanding of biological phenomena and strengthen their professional competencies.

Another important finding of the study concerns the role of reflective activities. Reflection sessions conducted at the end of laboratory classes enabled students to evaluate their own performance, identify mistakes, and determine ways to improve future learning activities.

Overall, innovative technologies enrich the content of Zoology laboratory classes, increase the interactivity of the educational process, and contribute to improving the professional preparation of future biology teachers.

CONCLUSION

The conducted research demonstrated that the use of innovative educational technologies in organizing Zoology laboratory classes is pedagogically effective and contributes to improving the quality of biology teacher education.

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Organizing Zoology laboratory classes through innovative technologies contributes to the development of students' knowledge, practical skills, and professional competencies.
2. Project-based learning, problem-based learning, and the STEAM approach serve as important pedagogical tools for increasing the effectiveness of laboratory instruction.
3. Virtual laboratories and digital technologies expand opportunities for studying biological objects and enhance the interactivity of laboratory activities.
4. Innovative educational technologies promote students' research skills, independent learning abilities, and professional development.
5. Reflective activities play a significant role in improving laboratory learning outcomes and fostering continuous professional growth.
6. The systematic integration of innovative technologies into Zoology laboratory classes contributes to improving the professional readiness of future biology teachers and strengthening the practical orientation of biology education.
7. Future studies should focus on exploring the educational potential of artificial intelligence technologies, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and advanced digital learning platforms in Zoology education and laboratory training.
8. Innovative educational technologies contribute to the development of students' research abilities, foster independent learning skills, and support the improvement of their professional competencies.
9. The implementation of reflective activities in Zoology laboratory classes positively influences students' self-assessment skills and professional growth.
10. The systematic use of innovative pedagogical technologies is essential for enhancing the professional preparation of future biology teachers.
11. Future research should focus on exploring the pedagogical potential of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and digital biological platforms in the organization of Zoology laboratory classes, as these represent promising directions for educational innovation.

The findings of this study can contribute to the improvement of laboratory instruction in biology education, the development of professional competencies among future biology teachers, and the overall enhancement of educational quality.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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2026. №5(5)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.